

D10.3

SPES Explorer

European Pressing

Issues Dashboard

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Disclaimer

This Working paper 10.3 for the project SPES has been prepared by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), as part as part of Work Package 10 “WP10 – Scenarios, stakeholder engagement and policies for the sustainability transition”. This Work Package aims to map and hierarchize the main synergies and trade-offs in country-level data by mapping the multidimensional correlations of a large set of policy and attainment variables drawn.

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1. About the Deliverable

The **SPES Explorer - European Pressing Issues Dashboard** is a web-based, interactive application that visualizes how citizens across European countries historically perceived their most pressing national problems over time. It offers country-level maps and time-series charts, with optional breakdowns by age and gender. Users can explore, compare, and download harmonized indicators derived from Eurobarometer surveys.

The current release candidate can be reached via <https://spes-test.shinyapps.io/spes-release/> and will be incorporated into the SPES website before end of project.

2. Unique Selling Point

The dashboard's core innovation is that it is based on **harmonized Eurobarometer time surveys**. Multiple survey waves are cleaned, recoded, and harmonized into consistent indicators so that **changes in public concern can be tracked comparably across countries and years**. This enables robust temporal analysis (e.g., rising concern about prices, immigration, or the environment) rather than one-off snapshots.

3. Link to SPES

SPES examines productivity, equity, sustainability, participation and human security. The dashboard **documents citizens' perspectives** by showing how people prioritize problems in their countries. It supports scenario building and policy dialogue by revealing shifts in perceived challenges that may motivate, accelerate, or constrain sustainable development pathways. In this sense, it is tightly connected to the work done in WP8 on citizens' perspectives and WP10 on the sociopolitical barriers in implementing sustainability transitions.

4. Summary of Methodology

- **Data source:** This dashboard draws on the Standard Eurobarometer survey, which asks respondents to identify up to two issues they consider most important facing their country. The Eurobarometer programme has been running since the 1970s as a long-standing cross-national survey series, commissioned by EU institutions and coordinated by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Communication. The data presented here spans 2003 to 2024.

In terms of geographic scope, the Standard Eurobarometer primarily covers EU and EC Member States, though Accession and Candidate countries appear intermittently, and there has been occasional EFTA participation as well. The UK has continued to be included in the Standard series following its withdrawal from the EU, though in general country participation can vary from wave to wave.

Microdata for research purposes are distributed through archives such as GESIS, ICPSR, and the CESSDA network. Accessing the underlying microdata typically requires free registration

through the GESIS Data Catalogue and is subject to their data access terms, including appropriate bibliographic citation. Some modules may be temporarily embargoed and unavailable in distributed datasets. It is worth noting that this dashboard presents only derived, aggregated indicators rather than respondent-level microdata.

Finally, the administrative boundary data used in the maps is © EuroGeographics, and any commercial use may require a separate licence.

- **Harmonization:** Raw responses from multiple waves are recoded to a stable concern taxonomy.
- **Indicators:** For each country–year, we compute the weighted **percent of respondents** naming each concern among their top two.
- **Breakdowns:** Disaggregations by **age** (Below 30, 30–60, Above 60) and **gender** (Male/Female) are produced for detailed analysis.
- **Geography & time:** EU Member States and selected partner countries across available Eurobarometer waves (coverage varies by wave). The app defaults to recent years where data exist.
- **Implementation:** R Shiny app using leaflet for mapping and ggplot2 for charts. Spatial geometries are served via GeoJSON; downloadable CSVs are generated server-side.
- **Quality assurance & limitations:** Indicators reflect **perceived** national issues (not objective conditions), and some waves may be **missing** for specific country–year pairs.

5. Sustainability and Future Outlook

- **Embedding:** The dashboard will be **embedded in the SPES website** and linked from relevant work-package pages and portals.
- **Updates:** It will be **updated in irregular intervals** whenever new Eurobarometer waves are cleaned and added as harmonized batches. Release notes and data vintages will be versioned.
- **Maintenance:** IIASA maintains code and data pipelines; minor UI/UX improvements can be added where appropriate.

6. Access and Reuse

All outputs present **aggregated, non-personal data**. Downloadable CSVs, plots and maps facilitate reuse in policy briefs, presentations, and modeling inputs. Source code can be upon request; full open access of the underlying microdata is not in line with standard Eurobarometer licensing.

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